

The Usage of Synonyms in English: Enhancing Language Skills and Communication.

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ABSTRACT

This article provides an overview of synonyms. Types of synonyms and the role of synonyms in language enrichment are also mentioned.

KEY WORDS.

Synonyms; Absolute synonyms; Partial synonyms; Near synonyms. Meaning of synonym in English.

A word or phrase that has the same or nearly the same meaning as another word or phrase in the same language. A synonym is a word that has the meaning as another word. For example, beautiful and attractive are synonyms of each other because they both refer to someone or something that looks good. Synonyms are a common part of every language, but they're especially useful when writing, whether you're writing a novel or a work email. Below, we explain how synonyms work and when to use them, along with the different types of synonyms. But first, let's take a more detailed look at this question. Synonyms are different words that have the same or similar meanings. They come in every part of speech, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and propositions. As a synonym example, let's look at synonyms for good. As one of the most commonly used words, good has a lot of synonyms that mean the same or almost the thing: fine, excellent, satisfactory, wonderful, superb. Notice how the meanings are not always identical; for example, excellent is a high degree of good, while satisfactory is more like a minimal amount of good. Still, the central idea is the same. All these synonyms refer to something that is positive and not bad. There are two main uses for synonyms, which will explain in detail below: .Synonyms can improve word choice, or choosing the single best word for what you're trying to communicate. .Synonyms are necessary to avoid over using the same word. First, synonyms are crucial for choosing the perfect word. While some language have only one word for one meaning, English use a variety of words to convey a single meaning, each with it's own unique and subtle distinction. This

variety of words is partly thanks to English usage of loan words, or words from other languages. Synonyms have three main types based on how close the words meanings are.

Absolute synonyms have the exact same meaning, partial synonyms have similar meanings with only subtle differences, and near synonyms have different meanings that are closely related to each other. Absolute synonyms Absolute synonyms are words meant exactly the same thing there is no difference in meaning. You can use absolute synonyms interchangeable; one synonym can replace another without changing the message.

Example:

identical- indistinguishable
drink- beverage insect-bug

Partial Synonyms Partial synonyms are words that mean almost the same thing, and the difference are only slight. What separates them can be a degree or amount, such as the difference between good and excellent, or one word can be a specific type of a more general word the way a puppy is still a dog. If you replace a word with it's partial synonym, the meaning changes a little, but the main message remaining the same.

Car- vehicle
run- sprint
big- gigantic

Near synonyms are words that have different meanings are still related. These words can't be used interchangeable, if you replace a word with a near synonym, the message becomes different. However, because they're related, a near synonym could a better and more accurate word choice the original. smart- witty river- creek hairy-furry Synonyms is the coincidence in the essential meaning of words which usually preserve their differences in connotations and stylistic characteristics. Synonyms are two or more words belonging to the same part of speech and possessing one or more identical or nearly identical denotational meanings, interchangeable in some contexts. These words are distinguished by different shades of meanings, interchangeable in some contexts . These words are distinguished by different shades of meanings, interchangeable in some contexts. These words are distinguished by different shades of meaning, connotations and stylistic features. The synonymic dominant is the most general term potentially containing the specific features

rendered by all the other members of the group. The words face, visage, countenance have a common denotational meaning “ the front of the head “ which makes them close synonyms. Face is the dominant, the most general word; countenance is the same part of the head with the reference to the expression it bears; visage is a formal word , chiefly literary, for face or countenance. In the series leave, depart, retire, clear out the verb leave , being general and most neutral term can stand for each of the other four terms. One must bear in mind that the majority of frequent words are polysemantic and it is precisely the frequent words that have many synonyms. The result is that a polysemantic word may belong in its various meanings to several different synonymic groups. Kharitonchic Z. gives the example of 9 synonymic groups the word part enters as the result of a very wide polysemy:

1) Piece, parcel, section, segment, fragment, etc; 2) member, organ, constituent, element, component, etc; 3) share, portion, lot; 4) concern, interest, participation, 5) allotment, lot, dividend, apportionment; 6)business, charge, duty, office, function, work; 7) side, party, interest, concern, faction; 8) character, role, cue, lines;9) portion, passage, clause, paragraph. According to whether the difference is in denotational or connotational component synonyms are classified into ideographic and stylistic(demographic synonyms denote different shades of meaning or different degrees of a given quality.

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